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Authors: Sorin Hermon & Raphael Moreau

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Authors (Partner)	CYI		
Responsible Author	Name: Sorin Hermon	Partner: CYI	

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Abstract

The deliverable "Report on integration of archaeological data in IPERION HS platforms, based on case studies" presents the results of test cases selected among the consortium partners to demonstrate cross-platform integration, addressing archaeological areas such as developments of ancient technologies, investigating dietary habits, movement of goods and people across time and space, and studying materiality, technique and style.

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Abbreviations

Abbreviations	Expansion
HS	Heritage Science
SLS	Structured Light Scanning
MAXRF	Scanning X-Ray fluorescence
RIS	Reflectance Imaging Spectroscopy
LIS	Luminescence Imaging Spectroscopy
THz	Terahertz Imaging
SIRT	Thermography Imaging
OCT	Optical Coherence Tomography
SQL	Structured Query Language
ICOM	International Council of Museums
CIDOC CRM	International Committee for Documentation of ICOM-Conceptual Reference Model

Narrative (technical) description

1. Introduction

Archaeological and paleontological research have a well-established record of relying on scientific data, through domain-related disciplines such as archaeological sciences. The development of new instruments, tools and methods advanced by Heritage Sciences opens new opportunities to archaeological research to mature its research processes and become a data-centric discipline. As scientific data and collection documentation regarding archaeological material proliferate, instruments, workflows, and methods for the integration of multimodal and multiscale data need to be developed. The importance of this issue is visible through several other EU-funded initiatives, such as the two other highly European interdisciplinary projects, ARIADNE+ and 4CH.

Archaeological data comes in a wide variety of formats, being the result of processes deriving from a multitude of methodologies associated with various disciplines and approaches, obtained at various levels, from satellite imaging to atomic force microscope and covering vast geographic areas or focusing on small parts of an artefact. Archaeology relies on methods common in cultural anthropology, earth sciences, mathematics or physics. On the journey to better understand the past and give it meaning in the present, the archaeologist, or the Cultural Heritage Specialist, must process data deriving from social sciences and the humanities and natural sciences as well, while often applying tools from the exact sciences. While archaeology *per se* focuses on the investigation of material culture remains from the past, modern research emphasizes the importance of a more inclusive approach, highlighting the impossibility to disconnect the material from the immaterial, the tangible from the intangible.

The figure below highlights the diversity of Cultural Heritage research, tackling, often contemporaneously, its multiple dimensions.

Consequently, each of these dimensions is addressed and investigated through a data-cycle that includes the identification, documentation, processing, post-processing, publication and archiving of a vast amount of heterogenous data and using multiple techniques, tools and methods, as described in the image below.

Moreover, the heritage landscape is by its own diversified and multi-layered, archaeologists facing the challenge to situate their research in these multiple dimensions, as shown in the image below.

Consequently, expanding the scope of archaeological research and including it in the conservation and valorization of Cultural Heritage narrative, as one of the scopes of the work here, and at a broader scale, E-RIHS, the European Research Infrastructure on Heritage Science, we face an additional challenge of data integration, as new disciplines join and bring in their contributions, as depicted in the figure below.

Such a multi-disciplinary effort requires data that is relevant for multiple approaches and in a broad range of applications, as exemplified in the figure below.

Thus, in order to jointly work and identify, document, analyze, interpret and archive Archaeological and Cultural Heritage data, we need to create virtual research environments that enable the access to data from heterogeneous sources and manipulate it in a variety of software environments, as shown below. Data should be described in such a way that researchers will be able to answer questions such as “is this data relevant to me?”, “is it useful to me?” “can I rely on this data?”.

The FAIR data principles, described below, are a big step forward towards achieving the above. However, they do not address the challenge of data quality, assessed through a clear description of its provenance, rather being principles enabling an efficient and collaborative data management.

Furthermore, recent developments in Artificial Intelligence (AI) highlighted the need for accurate, high-quality data, available in open formats and accessible to all. AI is an umbrella term that covers computer and data science processes known as Deep Learning, Machine Learning and Natural Learning Processes, all relying on high-quality datasets, as shown in the figure below.

When looking at the diagram above, a clear observation can be drawn: higher quantity and quality of data will enable computers to generate more accurate results based on AI processes. Therefore, we need to create virtual environments providing access to a large amount of data, which, on its turn, needs to be open to a peer-review, in order to assess its quality and relevance.

DIGILAB, one of the four platforms of E-RIHS, must build on these needs in order to align its organization and activity with latest technological developments in data sciences and the changing needs of its community of use. The figure below presents a schematic structure of DIGILAB:

Thus, it needs to allow the ingestion, curation, interrogation and publication of data, as below:

In more details, the ingestion process must address the following:

The curation of data should comply with these steps:

While the interpretation and publications of data should address the following:

This report presents case studies of multimodal and multiscale archaeological data integration to demonstrate cross-platform capabilities. Through the different selected cases, the integration of the results of different analyses conducted on the studied object allows for the generation of new knowledge and gives a different perspective on these artifacts.

The test cases were selected to represent the enormous diversity of materials and objects encountered in archaeology. The results and integration of these results illustrate the broad scope of scientific methods and analysis that can be used to study these artifacts.

2. Case studies

2.1 First case study: Pyrite Dinosaur project

The first case study presented here results from a MOLAB mission in the context of the Pyrite Dinosaur project. This project investigates the degradation of the pyrite in fossils from the Santa María de Ariño palaeontological site, which are conserved at the Dinópolis Museum in Teruel, Spain. In the scope of this project, a process of digital documentation and material characterization was conducted. 3D documentation allows for monitoring the structural changes due to environmental and climatic factors and studying the deformation and fracture mechanisms to evaluate the fossil's structural condition. The accurate measurements of the fossil's geometry, visualization of its textural details,

and quantitative shape analysis operation are made possible through the generated 3D model. The 3D documentation was realized with a Structured Light Scanner (SLS), an Aicon smartSCAN 3D system equipped with a 5.0-megapixel camera and set with close-range lenses featuring a field of view of 125 mm. The 3D model was generated from the acquired data using the native proprietary software Optocat Geomagic Wrap. The generated 3D model of a Crocodile cranial with surface texture color-enhanced with visualization filters is shown in Fig. 1.

The material characterization aims to better understand the elemental composition of the studied artifact. This will allow for better choices of environmental conditions to preserve the object and establish an in-depth diagnostic of the

Figure 1: snapshots of the 3D model of Crocodile cranial fossil obtained by using structured light scanning, and surface texture colour-enhanced with visualisation filters.

preservation state or degradation mechanism at stake. The material characterization was conducted with a Hydra XRF/XRD system (Fig. 2). The results of this operation confirmed the presence of iron and sulfur, along with other elements.

Figure 2: left, XRF/XRD data acquisition onto Crocodile cranial fossil, right, XRF spectrum of the point analysis

Integrating the results from different methods applied to the scientific study of this artifact allows for a new vision and better understanding of the global questions at stake.

2.2 Second case study: Andean wooden board

The second case study is based on the results of the analyses carried out on an ancient Andean wooden board (Fig. 3) conserved at the Museo delle Culture of Milan (MUDEC), Italy. It aims to see this object in a new light by providing a high-definition visualization of the artifact and exploiting dendrochronological data.

Figure 3: Inventory n° PAM 1349 – Federico Balzarotti Collection. Wood, Prosopis pallida, Peruvian north coast, length 16 cm, width 13 cm.

The multidisciplinary documentation performed on this object aims to investigate it through a set of analyses, thus providing an opportunity to see them in a new light. 3D documentation of the wooden object allows for monitoring the structural modification due to possible changes in environmental conditions and investigating the deformation and fracture mechanisms to evaluate the global structural condition of the object. Through the visualization of high-definition 3D models, details of micro-geometry and surface topological details are accessible, allowing reconstruction of the operational manufacture of the piece, thus contributing to stylistic and classification studies. Two methods were used to conduct the 3D documentation of the object: Structured Light Scanning (SLS) and Photogrammetry.

SLS was carried out with an Aicon 3D system smartSCAN, equipped with a 5.0-megapixel camera and set with close-range lenses featuring a field of view of 125 mm, thus aiming at the highest possible data recording. Acquisition of images for the photogrammetry technique was done using a Canon 80D and a Canon ef-s 18-135mm lens, set with 250 ISO and an aperture of F/22. The SLS-acquired data was processed using the native proprietary software Optocat and Geomagic Wrap, from which the 3D model was generated. The photogrammetry processing stage was completed using AdobeLightRoom proprietary software and Reality Capture software. Once the photogrammetric textured 3D model was created, CloudCompare software was used to combine, align, and project the RGB values from the photogrammetry model onto the SLS 3d model for the final model (Fig. 4). The photogrammetric process complemented well the SLS procedure as it allowed supplementing the missing part that SLS technique could not generate.

The generated 3D model allows for accurate dimensions and measurements of the object, allowing for various quantitative shape analyses. The texture added to the 3D SLS model is of great interest as it can be used to monitor wood color changes over time if environmental condition changes are reported.

Figure 4: The final combined 3D model of the wooden board PAM 1349 rendered in the open-source viewer MeshLab.

A dendrochronological analysis was carried out to complement previous radiocarbon dating analyses and provide a better understanding of the wood species used (Fig. 5). The investigation of wood species and ring boundaries was realized using Dino-Light digital microscopy. Upon caution analysis, the wood structure was found to fit with the *Prosopis Pallida* species.

Figure 5: a) transverse section of the wooden board, b) the section from the upper part of the transverse side that demonstrates clear ring boundaries, c) the detailed microscopic image demonstrates the ring boundaries behind the deteriorated surface, d) close-up microscopic look at the ring boundaries from the upper part of the transverse side.

Once again, this case study shows how data from different scientific methods were integrated to consider this precious archaeological artifact from new perspectives and points of view.

2.3 Third case study: Scarab from Hala Sultan Tekke, Cyprus

The third case study presents the results of the technical investigation of a scarab (Fig. 6) from the 14th season of excavation at the Late Bronze Age site of Hala Sultan Tekke, Cyprus, which allowed shedding light on the modes of production, techniques of manufacture and current condition state of these artifacts [1].

Figure 6: Scarab N794

The applied methodology to conduct the scientific examination of this artifact, scarab N794, consists of 3D documentation, generating a 3D model of the object realized with the SLS method with an Aicon 3D system smartSCAN, equipped with a 5.0-megapixel camera, and set with close-range lenses featuring a field of view of 125 mm. The SLS-acquired data was processed using the native proprietary software Optocat and Geomagic Wrap, from which the 3D model was generated. Visualization of the artifact in MeshLab software allowed us to show a perfect antithetic correspondence between the cavities and possible signs of single drilling by the craftsman. Using computer vision methods such as light filters and shaders allowed us to highlight the motif carved on the base of the scarab (Fig. 7).

Figure 7: a) 3D Model with light direction change enhancing background shapes b) MeshLab 'Radiance Scaling' shader with curvature colour enhancement c) 3D model of the N794 scarab

Material characterization was conducted using Digital Microscopy, XRF, and Visible Induced Luminescence (VIL). Digital microscopy examination was carried out with a HiroxKH8700 digital microscope equipped with an MXG-2500REZ lens (35-2500x). It revealed the presence of blue particles within one of the carved patterns (Fig. 8). This blue material was characterized using XRF and VIL to be identified as Egyptian blue. The small amount of these materials on this object raised the question of the intentional deposit of this pigment or external contamination. A blue bead, which analysis revealed to be also made of Egyptian blue, was found close to the N794 scarab during the excavation. Thus, a probable conclusion was the accidental contamination of the N794 scarab.

This third case study integrates data generated through the scientific examination of archaeological artifacts, allowing a better understanding of the object manufacturing process and ancient craftsmen's *savoir-faire*.

2.4 Fourth case study: Mural painting, Agios Ioannis Lambadistis, Cyprus

The fourth case study showcases the integration at the data level of data resulting from the scientific investigation of a mural painting located in the monastery complex of Agios Ioannis Lambadistis (St John Lambadistis), Cyprus. Integrating the different results allows a better understanding of the painting techniques and materials used and a diagnostic of the artifact's conservation state.

The studied mural painting (Fig. 9) is located on the north side of the southwest pier of the church dedicated to Saint Herakleidios in the monastery complex of Agios Ioannis Lambadistis (St John Lambadistis) situated in the village of Kalopanagiotis, in the Troodos mountains, Cyprus. The walls within the church are entirely painted, and the scenes are dated from the 11th to the 14th century [2], [3]. The monastery complex was granted World Cultural Heritage status by UNESCO in 2001, emphasizing its importance and value.

Figure 8: a) XRF spectrum of N794 scarab plain material b) Microscope image showing blue particles in the carved pattern of the scarab c) XRF spectrum of the blue particle d) VIL imaging displaying bright luminescence in near infrared region, characteristic of Egyptian blue pigment

A MOLAB mission conducted at the end of April and beginning of May with the cooperation of the Centre de Recherche et de Restauration des Musées de France (C2RMF) and the Laboratoire de Recherche de Monument Historique (LRMH) allowed to acquire a wide range of data of different modalities and different scales, with different purposes. The materiality of the painted artwork was investigated, and its spatial distribution was visualized by means of scanning X-ray fluorescence (MAXRF), Reflectance Imaging Spectroscopy (RIS), and Luminescence Imaging Spectroscopy (LIS). These data were obtained by the MITHRA scanner [4], [5], a particularly well-suited and innovative instrument for the point integration of such data as it allows a simultaneous acquisition of the described techniques. The stratified object's structural organization is investigated by Terahertz Imaging (THz). The conservation state diagnostic, inferred from the presence of an air pocket in an otherwise homogeneous material, is investigated using Thermography imaging (SIRT). The 3D point cloud of this part of the church was acquired using a Terrestrial Laser Scanner (TSL) model Surphaser 25 HSX, which is settled in a larger scale object describing the entire monastery complex. This information is necessary for conservation purposes, such as asset management or monitoring changes that could occur over time.

The 3D point cloud is the skeleton on which all the different datacubes are placed. Using the Python environment and the associated scientific library [6], the different datacubes were aligned by interpolating the 3D coordinates and adding these interpolated coordinates as new attributes to each datacube, thus referencing the position of each point of the different datacubes into a

standard reference frame. In doing so, multi-module and multi-scale data integration is integrated at the point level (Fig. 10 and Fig. 11).

Figure 10: Left, visible picture of the scanned area of the pier by means of the MITHRA scanner. Right, elemental maps of a) calcium (Ca), b) iron (Fe), c) mercury (Hg), d) lead (Pb), e) potassium (K), f) sulphur (S), g) silicon (Si), h) copper (Cu) and i) barium (Ba) generated with MITHRA scanner allowing investigation of the materiality of the mural painting.

In addition to these scientific data and all the knowledge generated through the interpretation of the results regarding materiality, knowledge from academic work of art history analysis, i.e., identification of the depicted figures, analysis of their clothing, etc. [7], [8] from different sources such as books, publications, or others, is also integrated.

Figure 11: Point level integration of the visible image and different elemental maps onto the 3D point cloud of the studied side of the pier. Innovative workflow allowing interpolation for a precise integration of the different data source was used.

To save all this information, a structured file in the HDF5 format was created. The HDF5 format [9] was chosen because it can store large sets of data and a wide range of types of data. It allows for

the structuring of stored data following a directory architecture. All the data were saved in a standard file, and the structure is presented in Fig. 12.

Figure 12: Directory architecture of the created file gathering the integrated data.

2.5 Fifth case study: icon from the Deryneia church, Cyprus

The fifth case study presents the results of integrating data from the scientific investigation conducted on a 16th-century dated icon from the Deryneia church (Fig. 13), Cyprus, depicting the birth of Christ. The integration aims to provide new insight regarding this object's materiality and painting technique.

Figure 13: Deryneia icon depicting the birth of Christ (Nativity)

Within the MOLAB mission described earlier, the MITHRA scanner was used to investigate the materiality of the painted artwork using MA-XRF, RIS, and LIS, and the layering structure, as well as the thickness of the painting layer was investigated using THz and Optical Coherence Tomography (OCT). Photogrammetry created the 3D point cloud of the artifact. Following the same workflow as the previous case study, the data from the different sources were aligned onto the point cloud. Once this aligned step was performed, the information obtained from each method was converted into a Geographic Information System (GIS) (Fig. 14), and a database containing all the information was built. This model allows the association of information between the database and the visualization on the map canvas (Fig. 15) and is of great interest as the information relative to each

point can be displayed, or a query over the entire model can be visualized through Structured Query Language (SQL) environment (Fig. 16).

Figure 15: Association of information from the database and visualization of the point (red dot) on the map canvas

Figure 16: Visualization of the points with a signal of Lead (Pb) superior at 98 counts by means of a SQL query filter.

3. Conclusion

The concept of chaine opératoire, coined several decades ago in order to frame the steps of research processes on investigating material culture remains, is at the core of developing heritage science-based archaeological research, where each step can be investigated through various tools and methods advanced by E-RIHS. The figure below describes typical chaine opératoire steps in investigating artefacts, the case-studies below demonstrating how applying heritage science methods following these steps enhance our understanding of the past.

Consequently, in order to integrate the archaeological process in the broader Heritage Sciences and thus expand the scope of E-RIHS, we propose a framework for describing heritage assets, including archaeological artefacts, that address current concepts of Cultural Heritage:

Each branch of the proposed description expands into further descriptions:

The subsequent documentation section describes in detail the instruments used and their experimental conditions when measurements were taken and processed, while provenance helps tracing the history of ownership of assets, where they were published and IP-related aspects. Through case studies, the multi-modal and multi-scale investigation of different artifacts representative of the wide range of materials encountered in archeology, we demonstrated the possibility of integrating various data types at a point level using innovative instruments and workflows. Such results should be integrated within the internationally accepted standard of the CIDOC CRM ontological model (Fig. 17) and the newly developed model of Heritage Digital Twin ontology [10].

Figure 17: Mapping to CIDOC-CRM of the different spectroscopy applied onto the Lambadistis Pilar

The above descriptions are instrumental in developing meaningful knowledge graphs that, together with the CIDOC-CRM ontology, would provide the envisioned data environment, built around the concept of semantic-aware heritage digital twins. Working with a broad range of archaeological artefacts and heritage assets, a few of which were described above, have led us to propose a digital environment that will enable a data-centric approach to archaeology and, in a broader perspective, Cultural Heritage:

1. 3D documentation of the geometry of the asset, and creation of a scaled 3D model.
2. Organise the database on the principles of the CIDOC-CRM ontology.
3. Create knowledge graphs describing the relations between data and derivative conclusions.
4. Map of all measurements and data on the 3D model, each with its relative coordinates.
5. Develop a visualisation system to volumetrically query the 3D model for its associated data.
6. Query the database and visualise the results on the 3D model.

The digital environment’s envisioned structure, as conceptually described in the report on the need to create the European Collaborative Cloud for Cultural Heritage Data, builds on a joint effort to create digital commons generated by the Heritage Digital Twins (HDT), ensure their digital continuum, by updates, uses and re-uses and the implementation of a Knowledge-Base for the use and re-use of HDTs and related tools. The image below summarizes the conceptual requirements for such a digital environment:

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